

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Exploring antifungal activities of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* extracts against human mucormycosis

Nagwa T. Elsharawy^{*1,2}, Afra Mohammed Baghdadi³, Amna A. Saddiq⁴, Ravi Naidu^{5,6}

¹Department of Movement Science & Health, College of Sport Science, University of Jeddah, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

²Department of Food Hygiene, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, New Valley University, Egypt

³University of Jeddah, Collage of Science, Department of Biology, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

⁴University of Jeddah, College of Sciences and Art Khulais, University of Jeddah, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

⁵Global Centre for Environmental Remediation (GCER), College of Engineering Science and Environment, the University of Newcastle, Callaghan, NSW, Australia

⁶Cooperative Research Centre for Contamination Assessment and Remediation of the Environment (CRC CARE), ATC Building, The University of Newcastle, Callaghan, NSW, Australia

Key words: Plant extract, Antifungals, Athel tamarisk, *Tetraena alba*, Aqueous extract, Methanolic extract

<http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/24.5.203-210>

Article published on May 11, 2024

Abstract

Recent studies concerned with various medicinal plant ingredients which have antimicrobial activities have directed special attention toward the pathogenic microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi. Fungal diseases severity increases in immunosuppressed persons, which impacts the public health. The purpose of this research was to study in vitro antifungal effects of some nontraditional medicinal plants in Saudi Arabia (*Tamarix aphylla*, *Zygophyllum album* and *Suaeda palaestina*) against some pathogenic fungi through extraction of the active ingredients of each plant (phenolics, flavonoids, etc.). The present research was conducted to evaluate antifungal activity of *T. aphylla* and *Z. album* leaf extracts against Mucormycosis “black fungus” pathogenic fungi. Leaves of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* were obtained, rinsed, dried, ground, and extracted using methanol (70%) and distilled water solvents. GC-MS analysis of the essential oil of plant extracts was carried out for antifungal activity assays. The results were aqueous extraction at 500 ppm mean measured at about 10 ± 0.40 mm, while aqueous extraction at 1000 ppm measured about 14 ± 0.70 mm; on the other hand, methanolic extraction at 500 ppm was about 16 ± 0.80 mm, and methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm detected about 23 ± 0.99 mm of *Tamarix aphylla* extraction. The inhibitory effect of *Zygophyllum album* in aqueous extraction at 500 ppm mean measured about 8 ± 0.22 mm, while aqueous extraction at 1000 ppm measured about 18 ± 0.60 mm; on the other hand methanolic extraction at 500 ppm was about 10 ± 0.41 mm, and methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm detected about 20 ± 0.56 mm. Obtained results indicated that *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* had nearly similar inhibitory effects, with slightly more patent effect of methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm *Zygophyllum album*.

* Corresponding Author: Nagwa T. Elsharawy ✉ dr.nagwa2004@yahoo.com

Introduction

COVID-19 has recently been linked to many significant issues, some of which are thought to be more hazardous than the coronavirus infection itself. Even though the majority of these infectious agents were quite insignificant in healthy individuals, they became deadly in combination with a coronavirus infection. *Mucormycosis* "black fungus," also known as *zygomycosis*, is related to *mucormycetes* mold types including *Mucor*, *Lichtheimia*, *Syncephalastrum*, *Rhizomucor*, *Apophysomyces*, *Rhizopus* and *Cunninghamella bertholletiae* species, which spread throughout the environment (decaying matter, soil, rotten wood, compost piles and leaves) and are considered one of the more dangerous rare fungal infections. The prevalence of this fungus has significantly increased among immunocompromised patients and those who take medications that impair immunity or reduce the body's natural defenses against pathogens (Martinelli *et al.*, 2021).

Infections such as *mucormycosis* can spread to the skin through burns, wounds, scrapes, and any type of skin incision, as well as after one inhales fungal spores from the environment. The spores that are inhaled mostly damage the sinuses and lungs after passing through the upper respiratory system. Depending on where in the body the fungus is developing, *mucormycosis* symptoms vary. Symptoms of rhinocerebral (sinus and brain) *mucormycosis* include headache, sinus or nasal congestion, immediately worsening black lesions on the nasal bridge or upper interior of the mouth, and fever. Fever, cough, chest pain, and shortness of breath are among the signs and symptoms of pulmonary (lung) *mucormycosis*. Blisters or ulcers may appear as a result of cutaneous (skin) *mucormycosis*, and the affected region may turn black. Pain, warmth, extreme redness, or swelling near a cut are further signs. The symptoms of gastrointestinal *mucormycosis*, on the other hand, include abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting as well as bleeding in the intestines. It might be challenging to determine which symptoms are caused by *mucormycosis* because diffused

mucormycosis generally affects persons who are already suffering from other illnesses. Patients who have a disseminated infection in the brain may experience changes in mental state or coma (Sharma and Goel, 2022).

The salt cedars (*Tamarix* spp.), which are invasive, exotic, deciduous, small trees and shrubs, are members of the Tamaricaceae family. The largest species of *Tamarix*, *Tamarix aphylla* (L.), which may reach heights of up to 18 meters, is found in Central Asia, North Africa, and Southeastern Europe (Abdallah and El-Ghazali, 2013; Sadafbibibi *et al.*, 2015). *T. aphylla* leaf extracts are utilized as an anti-inflammatory and antioxidant ingredient in the healing of wounds (Zain *et al.*, 2012; Iqbal *et al.*, 2013). The *T. aphylla* extract's phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of components such as glycosides, alkaloids, phenolics, tannins, and saponins (Emad and Gamal, 2013). *Zygophyllum album* L. (*Tetraena alba*) is a member of the *Zygophyllaceae* family, which is found in steppe and desert ecosystems from the Mediterranean to central Asia, South Africa, and Australia. The *Zygophyllum* genus is widely used in traditional medicine around the world for a variety of ailments, including the treatment of diabetes, wound care, dental caries treatment, and hair and face care, in addition to its anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antibacterial, and anticancer properties (Ebrahim *et al.*, 2018; Shawky *et al.*, 2019). The phytochemical components of *Z. album* include essential oils, phenolic compounds, triterpenes, flavonoids, and sterols (El-Shora *et al.*, 2016; Soumaya *et al.*, 2017).

Among the many methods for preventing fungal infections, chemical control is still one of the most important because it can reduce the incidence of fungal infections without the worry of secondary side effects or the development of microbial resistance to the chemicals. In order to safeguard coronavirus patients, researchers are looking for naturally occurring antifungal medicines that may be employed. The goal of the current study was to determine the antifungal efficacy of *Z. album* and *T. aphylla* leaf

extracts against pathogenic fungi that cause the "black fungus" disease *Mucormycosis*.

Material and methods

Plant collection

Leaves of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album*, about 1 kilogram from each plant, were collected during January 2021 from saline soil of the Taiba region (latitude: 21.7874726, longitude: 39.1459682), about 17 kilometers from the Red Sea. The collected plants were labeled and transported to the laboratories of the College of Science, University of Jeddah, where the obtained leaves were rinsed, dried, ground by blender, sieved using a 1mm aluminum sieve, and stored inside labeled airtight bottles until used (Seo *et al.*, 2014).

Plant extraction

Extraction techniques

Extraction techniques utilized four solvents: methanol (70%) and distilled water. Briefly for each solvent, 100g dry powder was extracted with 1000ml and 500ml solvents by maceration at room temperature for 48 hours. Then two filtrations of each mixture were run through N°1 Whatman paper and filter paper (0.45µm porosity). The collected filtrates were dried separately at 50°C using a Laborota 4000 rotary evaporator. Aqueous and aqueous methanol crude extract powder were used for investigate phytochemical compounds, determination of total phenol content and antioxidant screening (El-Shora *et al.*, 2014).

Test fungal organisms

The Test Fungal Organisms in the present study *Mucormycosis* "black fungus" were collected from Department of Microbiology, College of Science, University of Jeddah.

Antifungal activity examination

For antifungal activity assays, a stock solution was made for each extract with 0.2 g/mL in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The extracts were stored at 20°C until further use and the stock were stored at 4°C until used. The fungicidal activity of extracts was assessed by the agar well diffusion method using

Sabouraud's Dextrose Agar, incubated at 28±2°C/7d, and examined regularly for fungal growth to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) in millimeters (mm). The antifungal activity was repeated twice with two replicates for all clinical isolates with each plant extract at all the test concentrations (Indu *et al.*, 2006). The test extracts of desired concentrations (500 ppm, 1000 ppm) in Aqueous and methanolic solvents were each inoculated with an inoculum of 5mm diameter for each extract and incubated for seven days (Zohra *et al.*, 2013).

Electron microscope

Samples were fixed by gluteraldehyd 2.5% and dehydrated by ethanol with agitation using an automatic tissue processor (Leica EM TP, Leica microsistemas: Austria). Then the samples were dried using CO₂ in a critical point drier (Model: Audosamdri-815, Tousimis; Rockville, Maryland, USA). The sample was coated by a gold sputter coater (SPI-Module, USA). The samples were observed by scanning electron microscopy (model: JSM-5500LV; JEOL Ltd –Japan).

Statistical analysis

The data were expressed as means ± standard error (SE) and analyzed using SPSS 11.0 for Windows. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple comparisons were carried out to test any significant differences between the means. Differences between the means at the 5% confidence level were considered significant. Correlations between variables were computed using the regression model in SPSS 11.0 for Windows.

Results

Antifungal activity of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* extracts against *Mucormycosis* "black fungus"

Fig. 1 and Table 1 show the inhibitory effect of *Tamarix aphylla* in (I) were: (A1) Aqueous extraction at 500 ppm mean measured about 10±0.40 mm, while (A2) Aqueous extraction at 1000 ppm measured about 14±0.70 mm; on the other hand, (B1)

methanolic extraction at 500 ppm was about 16 ± 0.80 mm and (B2) methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm detected about 23 ± 0.99 mm. The inhibitory effects of *Zygothellium album* in (I) were: (A1) Aqueous extraction at 500 ppm mean measured about 8 ± 0.22 mm, while (A2) Aqueous extraction at 1000 ppm measured about 18 ± 0.60 mm; (B1) methanolic extraction at 500 ppm was about 10 ± 0.41 mm and (B2) methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm detected about 20 ± 0.56 mm.

Fig. 1. Antifungal activity of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygothellium album* extracts against Mucormycosis "black fungus": (I) represents *Tamarix aphylla*, while (II) represents *Zygothellium album*; (A1) Aqueous extraction at 500 ppm, (A2) Aqueous extraction at 1000 ppm, (B1) methanolic extraction at 500 ppm, (B2) methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm

Fig. 2. Scanning Electron Microscope of Antifungal activity of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygothellium album* extracts against Mucormycosis "black fungus": (A) represents the fungal cell at $\times 5000$, (B) represents the fungal cell at $\times 1000$

The effects of Tamarix aphylla and Zygothellium album extracts on the morphology of normal Mucormycosis "black fungus"

Fig. 2 shows the changes which occur by addition of different concentrations of *Tamarix aphylla* and

Zygothellium album extracts compared with the normal shape of Mucormycosis "black fungus" by the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) pictures at two different focal lengths: X5000 and X1000. Fig. A shows that the Mucormycosis "black fungus" appeared as ovoid "yeast" cells with budding. Although figure (B) shows the shape changes of the fungus cells and their colonies, this change started as shrinkage that appeared in the usual oval shape; also, the previous stacking of cells in the colony was lost when exposing Mucormycosis "black fungus" to *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygothellium album* extracts. Exposure to higher concentrations of the plant extracts led to deformation until the shape of cells completely disappeared and the colony cells were interfered with due to the severity of the deformation.

Table 1. Antifungal Assay of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygothellium album* extracts against Mucormycosis "black fungus"

Solvent	Conc.	<i>Tamarix aphylla</i>		<i>Zygothellium album</i>	
		500 ppm	1000 ppm	500 ppm	1000 ppm
Aqueous	Minimum	00	00	00	00
	Maximum	25	40	10	23
	Mean	10 ± 0.40	14 ± 0.70	8 ± 0.22	18 ± 0.60
Methanol	Minimum	9	13	00	00
	Maximum	28	34	15	25
	Mean	16 ± 0.80	23 ± 0.99	10 ± 0.41	20 ± 0.56

Discussion

An exponential growth rate of *mucormycosis* linked with COVID-19 has been observed. The capacity of the fungal spores to germinate in the favorable conditions created by COVID-19 patients' respiratory systems is the primary cause of the spread of this opportunistic fungal infection (Mahalaxmi *et al.*, 2021), which emerges once the patient's natural immunity is destroyed by the extremely contagious virus (Chauhan *et al.*, 2021). Numerous incidences of *mucormycosis* were documented in India in individuals recovering from COVID-19 who had a history of diabetes or other comorbidities. After an initial recovery, 37% of people with *mucormycosis* were found to have a history of COVID-19 (Hussain *et al.*, 2021). The fatality rate for *mucormycosis* was 50% before the COVID-19 epidemic. However, it has

increased to 85% during the current pandemic in India (Aranjani *et al.*, 2021).

Patients' development of a secondary opportunistic infection like *mucormycosis*, also known as a black fungus, during COVID-19 has been significantly influenced by their intermittent use of steroids, supportive oxygen from cylinders, and ventilators (in critically ill patients). *Mucormycosis* is a serious fungus infection that is angioinvasive and spreads quickly to other parts of the body. *Mucormycosis* can have devastating effects and be fatal to the persons who have it if it is not identified and treated quickly. In these situations, the patient needs immediate surgical intervention to stop other vital organs from becoming infected. Since mucormycosis is an opportunistic illness, it is frequently misdiagnosed and has a poor prognosis (Van *et al.*, 1999). Mucormycosis-causing pathogens are frequently diagnosed in low- and middle-income nations, including India, based on phenotypic traits such growth rate, colony morphology, and reproductive structures (Skiada *et al.*, 2018).

T. aphylla is a wild edible plant that is inexpensive and considerably improves human health in terms of disease treatment and prevention. *Tamarix aphylla* might be an excellent choice due to their strong efficacy in controlling plant diseases, which could lessen the risk to human health posed by some synthetic fungicides (Prakash *et al.*, 2019; Dilek *et al.*, 2021). The results of the current investigation showed that plants are a significant source of chemicals that may be helpful in the creation of novel antifungal medications. All of the examined plant extracts that were evaluated in various solvents showed varying levels of antifungal activity in a dose-dependent manner.

Antifungal activity of Tamarix aphylla and Zygophyllum album extracts against Mucormycosis "black fungus"

The inhibitory effect of *Tamarix aphylla* in (I) was (A1) Aqueous extraction at 500 ppm mean measured about 10 ± 0.40 mm., while (A2) Aqueous extraction at

1000 ppm measured about 14 ± 0.70 mm; on the other hand (B1) methanolic extraction at 500 ppm was about 16 ± 0.80 mm and (B2) methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm detected about 23 ± 0.99 mm. The inhibitory effect of *Zygophyllum album* in (I) was (A1) aqueous extraction at 500 ppm mean measured about 8 ± 0.22 mm, while (A2) aqueous extraction at 1000 ppm measured about 18 ± 0.60 mm; (B1) methanolic extraction at 500 ppm was about 10 ± 0.41 mm and (B2) methanolic extraction at (1000 ppm) detected about 20 ± 0.56 mm.

Similar results were reported by Pal *et al.* (2021), who assayed the antifungal properties of *T. aphylla* methanolic extract, which had antifungal activity ($97.68\% \pm 0.58$) against growth of *mucor spp.* and *F. oxysporum*, followed by ethanolic extract ($97.37\% \pm 0.33$) against *A. niger*. Palermo *et al.* (2020) regarded the antifungal potential of the ethanol extract of *T. aphylla* stems and leaves. Reid *et al.* (2020) mentioned that the crude ethanolic extract of *T. aphylla* leaves exhibited significant antifungal activity. The leaves' methanolic extracts from *T. aphylla* were recognized for their antiaflatoxic and antifungal actions. Similarly, the results of this study regarding the ethanol extract are in agreement with the findings of other authors (Skiada *et al.*, 2020; Eucker *et al.*, 2001; Ali *et al.*, 2019; Chander *et al.*, 2018; Alshehri *et al.*, 2021).

The effects of Tamarix aphylla and Zygophyllum album extracts on the morphology of normal Mucormycosis "black fungus"

Fig. 2 showed the changes which occurred through the addition of different concentrations of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* extracts compared with the normal shape of *Mucormycosis* "black fungus" using the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) pictures at two different focuses: X5000 and X1000. Fig. (A) showed that the *Mucormycosis* "black fungus" appeared as ovoid "yeast" cells with budding; figure (B) showed the shape changes of the fungus cells and their colonies. This change started by as shrinkage that appeared in the usual oval shape; also, the previous stacking of cells in the colony was lost

when exposing *Mucormycosis* “black fungus” to *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* extracts. Exposure to higher concentrations of the plant extracts led to deformation until the shape of cells completely disappeared and the colony cells were interfered with due to the severity of the deformation. These findings agreed with previous studies showing that the active components found in *T. aphylla* extract disrupted and altered fungal growth (Sarkar *et al.*, 2021; Singh *et al.*, 2021; Fatimah *et al.*, 2023).

Obtained results proved that *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* had nearly similar inhibitory effects, with slightly more potency of methanolic extraction at 1000 ppm for *Zygophyllum album*.

Acknowledgments

This article entitled “Exploring antifungal activities of *Tamarix aphylla* and *Zygophyllum album* extracts against human *Mucormycosis* “black fungus” contains the results and findings of a research project that was funded by Deanship of Research & Post-graduate of University of Jeddah Grant No. (UJ-21-ICI-8).

References

- Abdallah EM, El-Ghazali GE.** 2013. Screening for antimicrobial activity of some plants from Saudi folk medicine. *Global J. Res. Med. Plants & Indigen. Med.* **2**, 189–197.
- Adams RP.** 2004. Identification of Essential Oils Components by Gas Chromatography/ Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry. Allured Publishing Corporation, Carol Stream III, USA.
- Zohra M, Fawzia A.** 2013. Fungitoxic effect of natural extracts on mycelial growth, spore germination and aflatoxin B₁ production of *Aspergillus flavus*. *AJCS* **7(3)**, 293-298.
- Ali M, Alhazmi H, Ansari S, Hussain A, Ahmad S, Alam Md, Ali Md, El-Sharkawy K, Hakeem K.** 2019. *Tamarix aphylla* (L.) Karst. Phytochemical and Bioactive Profile Compilations of Less Discussed but Effective Naturally Growing Saudi Plant: Pharmacology and Therapeutic Uses. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-04408-4_16.
- Alshehri SA, Wahab S, Abullais SS, Das G, Hani U, Ahmad W, Amir M, Ahmad A, Kandasamy G, Vasudevan R.** 2021. Pharmacological Efficacy of *Tamarix aphylla*: A Comprehensive Review. *Plants* **11**, 118.
- Aranjani JM, Manuel A, Abdul Razack HI, Mathew ST.** 2021. COVID-19–associated mucormycosis: evidence-based critical review of an emerging infection burden during the pandemic’s second wave in India. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* **15(11)**, e0009921.
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0009921.
- Auribie MA.** 2011. Antioxidant activity of tannin from *Tamarix aphylla* leaves. *Basra J. Agric. Sci.* **24**, 1-10
- Badshah L, Hussain F.** 2011. People preferences and use of local medicinal flora in District Tank, Pakistan. *Med. Plants Res. Pak.* **5**, 22-29.
- Chander J, Kaur M, Singla N, Punia RPS, Singhal SK, Attri AK.** 2018. Mucormycosis: battle with the deadly enemy over a five-year period in India. *J Fungi (Basel)* **4(2)**, 46.
DOI: 10.3390/jof4020046.
- Chauhan N, Jaggi M, Chauhan SC, Yallapu MM.** 2021. Expert review of anti-infective therapy COVID-19: fighting the invisible enemy with microRNAs Abstract. *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther.* **19**, 137–146.
DOI: 10.1080/14787210.2020.1812385.
- Dilek A, Ozaras R, Ozkaya S, Sunbul M, Sen EI, Leblebicioglu H.** 2021. COVID-19-associated mucormycosis: case report and systematic review. *Travel Med Infect Dis.* **44**, 102148.
DOI: 10.1016/j.tmaid.2021.102148.
- Ebrahim T, Rasoul BZN, Saied K.** 2018. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Zygophyllum Qatarse* Hadidi leaf extract and evaluation of their antifungal activities. *JAPS* **8 (3)**, 168- 171.

- El-Shora HM, Abd El-Gawad AM.** 2014. Evaluation of allelopathic potential of *Rumex dentatus* root extract and allelochemicals on *Cicer arietinum*. *J. Stress Physiol. Biochem.* **10**, 177-180.
- El-Shora HM, El-Amier YA, Awad MH.** 2016. Antioxidant Activity of Leaf Extracts from *Zygophyllum coccineum* L. collected from Desert and Coastal Habitats of Egypt. *Int. J. Curr. Micro. App. Sci.* **5 (4)**, 635-641.
- Emad MA, Gamal EE.** 2013. Screening for antimicrobial activity of some plants from Saudi folk medicine. *Global J. Res. Med. Plants & Indigen. Med.* **2**, 189-197.
- Eucker J, Sezer O, Graf B, Possinger K.** 2001. Mucormycoses. *Mycoses* **44**, 253-260.
- Fatimah Al-Otibi, Ghaida A. Moria, Raedah I. Alharbi, Mohamed T. Yassin, Abdulaziz A. Al-Askar.** 2023. The Antifungal Properties of *Tamarix aphylla* Extract against Some Plant Pathogenic Fungi. *Microorganisms J.* **11**, 127.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11010127>.
- Hussain S, Riad A, Singh A, Klugarová J, Antony B, Banna H.** 2021. Global prevalence of COVID-19-associated mucormycosis (CAM): living systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Fungi* **7**, 985. DOI: 10.3390/jof7110985.
- Iqbal H, Khattak B, Ayaz S, Rehman A, Ishfaq M, Abbas MN, Malik MS, Wahab A, Imran, Mehsud S.** 2013. Pollution based study of heavy metals in medicinal plants *Aloe vera* and *Tamarix aphylla*. *J. Appl. Pharm. Sci.* **3**, 054-058.
- Mahalaxmi I, Jayaramayya K, Venkatesan D, Subramaniam MD, Renu K, Vijayakumar P.** 2021. Mucormycosis: an opportunistic pathogen during COVID-19. *Environ Res.* **201**, 111643. DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.111643.
- Martinelli L, Kopilaš V, Vidmar M, Heavin C, Machado H, Todorović Z, Buzas N, Pot M, Prainsack B, Gajović, S.** 2021. Face Masks During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Simple Protection Tool with Many Meanings. *Front. Public Health* **8**, 1-12.
- Muthu V, Rudramurthy SM, Chakrabarti A, Agarwal R.** 2021. Epidemiology and pathophysiology of COVID-19-associated mucormycosis: india versus the rest of the world. *Mycopathologia* **186**, 739-754. DOI: 10.1007/s11046-021-00584-8.
- Pal R, Singh B, Bhadada SK, Banerjee M, Bhogal RS, Hage N.** 2021. COVID-19-associated mucormycosis: an updated systematic review of literature. *Mycoses* **64**, 1452-1459. DOI: 10.1111/myc.13338.
- Palermo N.E., Sadhu A.R., McDonnell M.E.** 2020. Diabetic ketoacidosis in COVID-19: unique concerns and considerations. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* **105(8)**, dgaa360. DOI: 10.1210/clinem/dgaa360.
- Prakash H, Chakrabarti A.** 2019. Global epidemiology of mucormycosis. *J Fungi (Basel)*. **5(1)**, 26. DOI: 10.3390/jof5010026.
- Reid G, Lynch JP, Fishbein MC, Clark NM.** 2020. Mucormycosis. *Semin Respir Crit Care Med.* **41**, 99-114. DOI: 10.1055/s-0039-3401992.
- Sadafbibibi A, Afzal M, Kulsoombibi K, Shahanaaziz N, Abdur Raheem M.** 2015. Antifungal Activity of *Tamarix aphylla* (L.) Karst. Stem-bark Extract Against Some Pathogenic Fungi. *International Journal of Pharmacological Research* **5(2)**, 44-48.
- Sarkar S, Gokhale T, Choudhury SS, Deb AK.** 2021. COVID-19 and orbital mucormycosis. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* **69**, 1002-1004. DOI: 10.4103/ijo.IJO_3763_20.

- Sharma A, Goel A.** 2022. Mucormycosis: risk factors, diagnosis, treatments, and challenges during COVID-19 pandemic. *Folia Microbiol (Praha)* **26**, 1-25.
- Shawky E, Gabr N, Elgindi M, Mekky R.** 2019. A Comprehensive Review on Genus *Zygophyllum*. *Journal of Advanced Pharmacy Research* **3(1)**, 1-16.
- Singh AK, Singh R, Joshi SR, Misra A.** 2021. Mucormycosis in COVID-19: a systematic review of cases reported worldwide and in India. *Diabetes Metab Syndr* **15(4)**, 102146. DOI: 10.1016/j.dsx.2021.05.019.
- Skiada A, Lass-Floerl C, Klimko N, Ibrahim A, Roilides E, Petrikkos G.** 2018. Challenges in the diagnosis and treatment of mucormycosis. *Med Mycol.* **56**, 93–101.
- Skiada A, Pavleas I, Drogari-Apiranthitou M.** 2020. Epidemiology and diagnosis of mucormycosis: an update. *J. Fungi (Basel)* **6(4)**, 265. DOI: 10.3390/jof6040265.
- Soumaya B, Wided M, Riadh K.** 2017. The Halophytic Genus *Zygophyllum* and *Nitraria* from North Africa: A Phytochemical and Pharmacological Overview. DOI: 10.1007/978-94-024-1120-1_13.
- Van Steenweghen S, Maertens J, Boogaerts M, Deneffe G, Verbeken E, Nackaerts K.** 1999. Mucormycosis, a threatening opportunistic mycotic infection. *Acta Clin Belg.* **54(2)**, 99-102. DOI: 10.1080/17843286.1999.11754215
- Zain ME, Awaad AS, Al-Outhman MR, El-Meligy RM.** 2012. Antimicrobial activities of Saudi Arabian desert plants. *Phytopharmacol.* **2**, 106-113.